

ON THE FORMATION AND STABILITY OF BICARBONATES OF THE METALS OF THE GROUP II OF THE MENDELÉEF'S PERIODIC TABLE

By K. C. GROVER

The acid carbonates of Be, Mg, Zn, Cd and Hg have been isolated for the first time in the solid state, and have also been stabilized. The stability of the bicarbonate of Zn, Cd and Hg (II B group) decreases with decreasing electro-positive character of these metals.

In group II of the Mendeleef's Periodic Table, Keiser and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 1711) investigated only the acid carbonates of calcium and barium, and Haider, Aziz and Langer (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 178) that of strontium. They succeeded in isolating the solid compounds at a lower temperature and found them to possess the compositions $\text{CaCO}_3 \cdot 1.75 \text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$; $\text{BaCO}_3 \cdot 1.5 \text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$ and $\text{SrCO}_3 \cdot 1.60 \text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$. In order to advance the study of these compounds of the remaining elements of the group, the acid carbonates of Be, Mg, Zn, Cd and Hg have been investigated. Mostly these exist in solution only and at low temperatures.

However, Haider *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) claimed to have found a method of stabilizing the bicarbonates of strontium and lithium. The method was tried in the case of the bicarbonates, under investigation, and it was found that a certain degree of stabilisation could be attained.

EXPERIMENTAL

The bicarbonates of the elements—Be, Ba, Sr, Zn and Cd—being less soluble in water are precipitated from their aqueous solutions, while the bicarbonates of Ca, Mg and Hg are less soluble in alcohol in the presence of which they are precipitated.

The bicarbonates of Be, Mg, Zn, Cd and Hg were therefore prepared by mixing solutions of potassium bicarbonates with the corresponding chlorides of the metals, all cooled to 0°. It was observed that Hg $(\text{HCO}_3)_2$ was precipitated only by the addition of alcohol to the mixed solution and for precipitating Mg $(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, a large quantity of absolute alcohol was required. The precipitates were washed successively with ice-cold water, saturated with CO_2 , alcohol and ether, and dried at 0°.

A. The decomposition temperature of each of the above precipitates was found by gradually raising the temperature of the ice-cold water-bath inside which the boiling tube containing the precipitate was placed. The decomposition temperature was recorded when the CO_2 evolved from the precipitate on passage through a little lime water just turned the latter turbid.

TABLE I

No.	Bicarbonates.	Decomposition temperature		
		without gelatin.	with 5% gelatin.	with 2% gelatin.
I	Be $(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	7°	10°	13°
II	Mg $(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	5°	8°	10°
III	Zn $(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	11°	14°	18°
IV	Cd $(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	5°	8°	11°
V	Hg $(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	2°	5°	°

From above, it is found that the decomposition temperatures of these bicarbonates are raised

- (i) by the presence of gelatin and,
- (ii) by increasing concentration of gelatin.

B. The ratio of CO_2 to the oxide in these precipitates was determined by the method of Keiser and MacMaster (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 1715) as improved by Haider *et al.* However, a few modifications were made such as :—

(a) A sulphuric acid tower was interposed between the bottle containing water (to dissolve vapours of HCl gas) and the tube for absorption of CO_2 . The function of this sulphuric acid tower is to dry the CO_2 on its passage to the saphnolite tube where it is to be absorbed.

(b) Saphnolite was substituted for a solution of potash and was found to be a better absorbent of CO_2 . This did away with the possibility of the formation of potash solution from potash bulbs being sucked by the suction applied, when potash bulbs were used for absorbing CO_2 .

(c) A weighed calcium chloride tube was fitted after saphnolite tube in order to absorb any moisture coming from saphnolite, thus checking any source of error liable to be caused by any moisture contained in the saphnolite itself.

(d) Suction was applied after the experiment in order to drive out any CO_2 left in the bottle containing water.

The ratio of CO_2 to that of oxide determined as above, in each case, was found to be as follows :—

(i)	$\text{Be}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	$\text{CO}_2 : \text{BeO} = 2.62$
(ii)	$\text{Mg}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	$\text{CO}_2 : \text{MgO} = 2.20$
(iii)	$\text{Zn}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	$\text{CO}_2 : \text{ZnO} = 2.74$
(iv)	$\text{Cd}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	$\text{CO}_2 : \text{CdO} = 2.72$
(v)	$\text{Hg}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	$\text{CO}_2 : \text{HgO} = 2.10$

An alternative determination of the ratio CO_2 : oxide in a solution of the acid carbonate of each of these metals by the turbine method (after Langer) gave the same values as above.

The formulae derived for these bicarbonates on the basis of these observations and calculations are as follows :

- (i) $\text{Be}(\text{HCO}_3)_2 \cdot 0.65 \text{CO}_2$.
- (ii) $\text{Mg}(\text{HCO}_3)_2 \cdot 0.20 \text{CO}_2$.
- (iii) $\text{Zn}(\text{HCO}_3)_2 \cdot 0.74 \text{CO}_2$.
- (iv) $\text{Cd}(\text{HCO}_3)_2 \cdot 0.72 \text{CO}_2$.
- (v) $\text{Hg}(\text{HCO}_3)_2 \cdot 0.10 \text{CO}_2$.

The net increase in weights was calculated in the case of the carbonates of all these metals after keeping them to constant weights firstly in an atmosphere of CO_2 and mois-

ture and secondly over calcium chloride. The results show that bicarbonate formation by the direct absorption of CO_2 by the carbonates of the metals of Group II does not occur in the case of beryllium, magnesium, strontium and zinc, but takes place to a slight extent in the case of calcium (19.09%), barium (9.63%), cadmium (8.65%) and mercury (7.23%), which values, no doubt, are far below the theoretical absorption necessary for the formation of bicarbonates.

A stable form of the bicarbonate of these metals was prepared by precipitating a solution of the respective carbonate in carbonated water, containing galatin, by means of absolute alcohol. These precipitates did not decompose at the ordinary temperature of the laboratory, while the other preparations rapidly decomposed above their respective decomposition temperatures. It is desirable to extend this method of stabilisation to other unstable compounds.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
GORAKHPUR INTERMEDIATE
COLLEGE, GORAKHPUR, U. P.

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